

Elucidation of molecular features associated with progression of Monoclonal Gammopathies to Multiple Myeloma

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Multiple Myeloma is a chronic malignancy characterized by slow progression and recurrences. Currently there is no effective cure since eventually the disease develops resistance to all the available therapeutic approaches. Although recent advances have expanded our understanding of the cellular functions associated with health to disease transition, recurrence and response to therapy, critical aspects of this complex pathology remain to be elucidated [1].

MGUS (monoclonal gammopathy of undetermined significance) is present in 3-5% of the ageing European population and every year, 1% progress to incurable MM that imposes a significant burden on EU societies and health systems. Thus, the best chances of curing MM may be in preventing its progression in the first place.

Application of proteomics and bioinformatics approaches on comprehensively annotated samples obtained from all informative states ([MGUS], smoldering MM [sMM], active MM [MM]) allowed us to identify biological pathways and molecules responsible for the onset, progression and resistance to therapy of Multiple Myeloma.

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